

Tribal Christianity (and allied castes) in the Himalayas

By Stephen Christopher, Tokyo Metropolitan University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Anglican, Himalayan Christianity, Tribal Christianity, Dalit Christianity, Protestantism, Catholic

X

Date Range: 1950 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Himalayan tribal Christianity (and tribal-allied groups)

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, Nepal, Bhutan, India, North India, Himalayas, Northeast India

The spread of Christianity (predominately Anglican, Catholic and United Evangelical Lutheran) into the Himalayan region and among tribal and tribal-aligned communities at its greatest extent in the contemporary period.

参与者的状态

✓ 非精英 (普通人, 普通民众)

来源

理解这一问题的书面资料：

- Source 1: Cox, Jeffrey. 2002. *Imperial Fault Lines: Christianity and Colonial Power in India, 1818-1940*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.
- Source 2: Ripert, Blandine. 2002. "Improbable Globalization: Individualization and Christianization among the Tamangs." In *Facing Globalization in the Himalayas: Belonging and the Politics of the Self*, edited by Gerrard Toffin and Joanna Pfaff-Czarnecka, 45-62. London: Sage Publications.
- Source 3: Webster, John C.B. 2007. *A Social History of Christianity: North-west India Since 1800*. Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Notes: Taken together, these scholarly works describe the historical interplay of Christian missionaries and colonial power in the Punjabi foothills of the Himalayas, the effects of rapidly-rising Christian affiliation among Tamang (loss of traditional authority and increased individualism, among others), and a historical overview of Christianity in a broader context. For other important works on Scheduled Tribal Christianity in South Asia and especially the Himalayas, see: 1. Augustine, Sali. 2011. "Violence against Christians in India: Mobilization of Adivasis and Dalits as the Un-reached and the Foot-soldiers." *The Journal of Sophia Asian Studies* 29(39-54). 2. Hedlund, Roger E. 2000. *Christianity is Indian: the emergence of an indigenous community*. Mysore: ISPCK. 3. Chaube, S.K. 1999. "The Scheduled Tribes and Christianity in India." *Economic and Political Weekly* 34(9):524-526. 4. Roy-Burman, B K. 1972. "Integrated Area Approach to the Problems of the Hill Tribes of the North-East" in K Suresh Singh *The Tribal Situation in India*. Indian Institute of Advanced Study, Shimla. 5. Sinha, Surajit Chandra. 1982. "Tribal Solidarity Movements in India: A Review" in Buddhadev Chaudhuri *Tribal Development in India*. 6. Minz,

Nirmal. 1997. *Rise up, my people, and claim the promise: the Gospel among the tribes of India*. Delhi: Indian Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge. 7. Christopher, Stephen. 2018. "Dalit Margins: Tribal Belonging and State Recognition in the Western Himalayas." PhD diss., Syracuse University. 8. *Margins of Faith: Dalit and Tribal Christianity in India*. 2010. Edited by Rowena Robinson & Joseph Marianus Kujur. Delhi: Sage Publications.

理解这一问题的在线资料:

– Source 1 URL: <https://web.library.yale.edu/divinity/himalayan>

– Source 1 Description: Created in 2008, the Himalayan Mission Archive Collection at the Yale Divinity School Library. It includes the archives of Christian organizations operating in the Himalayas. Included is The Nepal Church History Project, a 1985 Nepalese project to preserve church history; The International Nepal Fellowship, which preserves health-related documents by a Christian medical NGO; the Central Asia Fellowship, founded in 1989 in order to convert Tibetan Buddhists living throughout the Himalayas; and The United Mission to Nepal, an INGO started in 1954 dealing with health and agriculture.

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.bridgeinternational.org/reaching-the-himalayas-for-jesus-christ-by-dawa-singye-bhutia/>

– Source 2 Description: An example of an American-Scandinavian Evangelical NGO. Their motto is "Linking God's People to Reach the Unreached". Although global in scope, it includes posts about Christian missionary work in the Himalayas -- such as the above testimonial by a Bhutanese former Tibetan Buddhist and his description of the spread of 200 house churches under the auspices of the Free Church of Finland Mission.

– Source 3 URL: <http://www.missioninchurch.org/>

– Source 3 Description: A small-scale, Kathmandu-based missionary group. Founded by David Prasai, it is representative of many such grassroots Christian movements in the Himalayas.

Notes: Taken together, these resources span an archival database of major Christian missionary efforts, an example of Western-backed missionary efforts in the region, and an indigenous missions group focused on small-scale house churches.

相关的在线的原始文本资料库(使用原语言和/或翻译)

– Source 1 URL: gaddi.in

– Source 1 Description: A Gaddi-language website for biblical study created by Christian converts among the Hali sub-caste of the Gaddi community.

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.nepalbiblesociety.org/site/>

– Source 2 Description: Based in Kathmandu, NBS is an online resource provided through United Bible Societies (UBS). It went online as an officially-registered NGO in 2007, although it was created in 1975. It provides Nepali-language biblical resources (textual and audio) and gives news and updates regarding Christian observances.

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/nepalichristianmedia/>

– Source 3 Description: A community Facebook page with over 25,000 subscribers of Nepalese Christians. It is described as "a common place where Nepali Christians can share, participate, request prayers and build up their own community profile." The Facebook page has 100s of uploaded videos and pictures showing Nepalese Christian worship conferences and teachings.

Notes: A representative sample of an indigenous effort to promote Christianity within a small tribal dialect (Gaddi), a large-scale effort to promote Christianity in a national language (Nepalese), and a social

network of Himalayan Christians.

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bPAoLiZPUvY>

– Source 1 Description: Ladakh Buddhist Association interrogation of a blind Christian Ladakhi who was beaten by locals (allegedly LBA employees) and pressured to reconvert to Buddhism. Such videos are common throughout the Himalayas and are used by both parties: Christians to show persecution and non-Christians (usually Hindus and Buddhists) to show social breakdown due to coercive conversion tactics.

一般变量

成员/团体互动

其他宗教团体与该宗教之间有文化上的接触吗：

– Yes

↳ 这种文化接触是竞争性的吗：

– Yes

Notes: The Christianization of Himalayan tribal groups often runs into cultural contestation with traditional forms of knowledge and sociality. For example, the Christian Lepchas in Darjeeling District and in southern Sikkim face intense criticism from Buddhist Lepchas (see "Vanishing Lepcha: Change and Cultural Revival in a Mountain Community of Sikkim" by Jenny Bentley in the Bulletin of Tibetology).

↳ 文化接触是兼容并包/多元的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Even in the Lepcha case described above, Buddhists and Christians are still integrated in village dynamics. Virouland (2004) argues that Magar converts in Nepal experience Pentecostalism as congruent with Tibeto-Burman shamanistic possession rituals. Christianity is seen as revitalizing and integrating extant syncretistic practices and not as a conceptual departure. Likewise, Blandine Ripert (2014) cites Nima Ghising, a globetrotting Tamang pastor whose sermons are widely disseminated on YouTube, as arguing for the conceptual crossover of Tamang and Christian themes of malign spirits and the afterlife. These harmonizing aspects of Christianity within a tribal milieu suggests pluralism and accommodation, not cultural rupture and group competition.

↳ 文化接触是中立的吗：

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, Christian conversion is treated neutrally by the dominant tribal community. This may be due to relative ignorance about what Christianity is and how it is practiced (as is the case among Gaddis, a Hindu tribe in Himachal Pradesh). Gaddi tribals are caste Hindus who often disregard the low-status Gaddi groups who convert to Christianity. This disregard is not necessarily negatively coded and can be described as neutral cultural contact.

↳ (在采样地区内)有暴力冲突吗：

– Yes

Notes: See Nicholas Gier's "The Origins of Religious Violence" (2014, Lexington Books) for state violence against Bhutanese Christians during the First Shabdrung. On the other hand, alleged violence enacted by Christians in the Himalayas is documented here (<http://christianaggression.org/2016/04/27/the-spread-of-christianity-in-kashmir-and-its-unholy-designs/>). In India, the VHS, BJP and even the Congress in Himachal Pradesh routinely warn the legislature about the danger of Christian conversion and their coercive tactics (warnings that fuel anti-Christian violence).

↳ (与采样地区外的族群)有暴力冲突吗：

– Yes

Notes: Christians are generally a persecuted minority in India and face extreme violence by Hindu extremists. For a scholarly review of the situation across India, see Chad Bauman's "Hindu-Christian Conflict in India: Globalization, Conversion and the Coterminal Castes and Tribes" (The Journal of Asian Studies 72(3):633-53).

该宗教团体有确认入会的一般性程序/制度吗：

– Yes

↳ 与生俱来（成员身份在这种社会是默认的）：

– No

Notes: Although Christian affiliation is based on personal conviction at the theological level, in everyday practice it is often assumed at birth and correlates with caste/clan affiliation. Anglicans and Catholics may be more likely to consider their religious belief default if born into such a family, while Protestants and Evangelicals may emphasize the importance of children taken personal declarations of faith to be formally inducted into the Christian community.

↳ 基于个人选择：

– Yes

Notes: Many Evangelical and Protestant tribal Christians emphasize the personal choice of religious conviction and de-emphasize the strong correlation between clan belonging and Christian conversion. In short, caste/clan groups may convert to Christianity en masse and create strong communal ties to the faith that in a sense de-emphasize personal choice.

↳ 由社会阶层赋予：

– Yes

Notes: For example, Halis are both the lowest caste and class of the Gaddi community (in Chamba and Kangra Districts of Himachal Pradesh) and the most likely to convert to Protestantism. See Stephen Christopher's PhD dissertation Tribal Margins, especially Chapter 4 Protestant Promises: Spiritual Torment and Aspirational Hermeneutics.

– Yes

Notes: For example, Halis are both the lowest caste and class of the Gaddi community (in

Chamba and Kangra Districts of Himachal Pradesh) and the most likely to convert to Protestantism.

↳ 由特定年龄阶段赋予：

– No

↳ 由性别赋予：

– Yes

Notes: Nathaniel Roberts's "To Be Cared For" (2016, 186) describes "two ways of conceptualizing spiritual power" among house churches in Chennai slums: "The first was overt and hierarchical and centered on the person of the pastor. Of equal or greater significance, however, were quasi-autonomous organizational networks among church women". These two bases of spiritual authority – literate and charismatic male pastors hooked into NGOs and church congregants, largely women, who draw on experiential authority and local prestige – exist in a sometimes complementary, sometimes combative dialectic (Roberts 2016, 186). He goes on to attribute the lopsidedness of female Christian devotion to structural dependence on men, poverty, and higher rates of self-reporting worry. Although his work is grounded in Chennai, it certainly holds true to Himalayan tribal Christian affiliation, as well.

↳ 由参与特定仪式赋予：

– Yes

Notes: Tribal Christians in the Himalayas participate in the expected range of rituals of belonging: 1) Baptism (based on Matthew 28:19) as a mode of church initiation that follows in the biblical account of Jesus receiving baptism from John the Baptist; 2) Confirmation as a sacrament of strengthening the grace of the Holy Spirit; and 3) the Eucharist (Holy Communion, prabhu bhoj in Hindi) as a monthly affirmation of the Christian community and anticipation of the return of Christ in body. While these rituals often mark Christian/Catholic participation among Himalayan tribals, others emphasize the need for personal conversion through accepting Christ into one's heart. For these Christians (often Evangelicals), testimonials of miraculous conversion are central markers of participation. For example, Hali Christians among the Gaddi community emphasize the conversion testimonial as an important ritual marker of belonging.

↳ 由其它因素而赋予：

– Yes [specify]: Class, gender, ritual and personal choice are all important factors in tribal Christian belonging in the Himalayas. In addition, caste and clan are important matrices for understanding conversion among tribals.

宗教团体积极宣教、招募新成员吗：

– Yes

↳ 对宗教专职人员来说，发展信众是强制性的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Not exactly mandated, but Christian tribal pastors and leaders often proselytize based on their inner conviction of the importance of salvation. This is often attributed to Matthew 28:19 and the injunction to "make disciples of all nations."

↳ 所有信徒都必须发展信众吗：

– Yes

Notes: Again, biblical passages are proffered among Evangelical and Protestant Christian tribals and tribal aspirants about the need to spread the "good news" of Christianity. Among the Hali Christian converts within the Gaddi community, the case study I know best, adherents were often implored through weekly sermons at house churches to set good examples for Hindu neighbors. The intensity of proselytizing depended on individuals. However, it is not a safe legal environment to conduct missionary work in Himachal Pradesh. Himachal Pradesh is the first Congress-led state to adopt anti-conversion legislation, a move widely understood to be politically motivated. Without a single registered case of forced conversion, Chief Minister Vibhadra Singh warned that "unless checked well in time this practice may erode the confidence and mutual trust between the different ethnic and religious groups in the state" (Tribune News Service, 2006).

↳ 宗教专职人员必须传道吗：

– No

Notes: Not in the sense of conducting extensive missionary work. Opening a village house church is often the strategy of Christian leaders.

↳ 所有信众都必须传道吗：

– No

Notes: Most Himalayan tribal Christians are unable to conduct extensive missionary work, either at home or abroad, due to financial restraints and family responsibilities.

↳ 发展信众是强制的吗：

– Yes

↳ 这种强制性行为诉诸武力吗：

– No

↳ 这种强制性行为通过经济上的制裁来实现吗：

– Yes

Notes: Not sanctions, but inducements. This is not all the time. I was struck by indigenous Christian tribal communities that offer not economic inducements but rather protection from witchcraft and spiritual torment. However, there certainly are cases of economic and psychosocial pressures put on tribals to convert. Such converted individuals are sometimes dubbed "Rice Christians". This phrase was coined by Thomas Hale Jr, a physician and missionary in Nepal. He described the injustice of converting tribals by exploiting their social condition and offering material allurements (i.e. rice)

for conversion.

宗教有官方的政治支持吗：

— No

Notes: It is more often the case that Himalayan states and nations actively promote anti-conversion laws to prevent the Christianization of predominately Hindu and animist groups. In Bhutan, for example, Article 7 of the 2008 constitution guarantees religious freedom while forbidding conversion "by means of coercion or inducement". Such a clause is often pretext to target Christianity, sometimes without strong cause. A similar law was passed in Himachal Pradesh recently without a registered case of coercive tactics to convert tribals to Christianity.

在该宗教中存在叛教的概念吗：

— No

Notes: In cases where Christian belonging closely parallels clan and caste affiliation, apostasy is rarely (if ever) a matter of public denunciation/abandonment of faith because it is so intimately tied to social networks and social belonging.

大小和结构

在样本区域中的宗教团体信奉者人数(估计人口，数字)

— Estimated population, numeric: 5500000

Notes: It is very difficult to accurately estimate the population of Christian tribals in the Himalayas. In Nepal, Christianity is the 5th most practiced religion (2011 census) with 375,699 adherents, or 1.4% of the population. But this may be severely under-reported, and others estimate over 1,000,000 Christians in Nepal. Sikkim has 9.9% Christianity (2011 census) -- mostly members of the Evangelical Presbyterian Church of Sikkim -- approximately 61,000 members. Bhutan has .9% Christianity -- approximately 12,255 members (according to Aide à l'Eglise en détresse). Himachal Pradesh has .18% Christianity. Kashmiri Christians number in the hundreds and face intense governmental and social pressure. See: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/Kashmir-zealots-push-Christians-into-valley-of-fear/articleshow/11595441.cms>. In the Northeast of India, Christianity has a strong presence: 1,851,290 Baptists, 1,711,495 Catholics, and 1,405,781 Presbyterians. In Uttarakhand, Christianity is 0.37%.

样本区域中的宗教团体的信奉者数量(在样本区域人口中的百分比，数字)

— Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1

Notes: There are about 52,000,000 people in the Himalayas and as many as 450,000,000 settled around the base of the Himalayas. Among this population, a fraction is Scheduled Tribe or aligned to tribal identity.

经典

宗教团体有经典吗：

经典是一个统称，指的是受到尊崇、与其它文本相比被认为具有特别的权威性和神圣性的文本。严格意义上经典指书写的文本，但是也存在“口述经典”（比如印度的吠陀经典）。

– Yes

↳ 它们是书面的吗：

– Yes

Notes: Many efforts are underway to provide the Bible in tribal languages.

↳ 它们是口述的吗：

– Yes

Notes: As many tribals are non-literate, Christian missionaries often provide audio transcription of the Bible in tribal languages.

↳ 经典的来源和一个（或一组）故事有关吗：

– Yes

↳ 由至高无上的神揭示：

– Yes

Notes: Revealed by God the Father to Moses and later apostles.

↳ 由其他超自然生灵揭示：

– No

↳ 由至高无上的神启示：

– Yes

Notes: It is believed by highly literate and scholarly Christians that God the Father inspired the selection of texts to be included in the biblical canon at the First Council of Nicaea. Similarly, Athanasius, Bishop of Alexandria, was inspired by God when he formally organized the New Testament canon.

↳ 由其他超自然生灵启示：

– No

↳ 来源于神或半神半人：

– No

Notes: Biblical patriarchs and church leaders were not divine in any sense but in a special albeit human covenant with God.

↳ 来源于凡人：

– Yes

建筑，地理

是否存在纪念性的宗教建筑物：

– Yes

↳ 在一般的定居地，所有宗教纪念性质建筑、纪念物面积所占百分比是多少：

– Percentage: 0

Notes: Colonial-era churches remain in Himalayan hill stations not destroyed by the massive Kangra Earthquake of 1905. These monuments are still used by Christians in the Himalayas -- tribal and non-tribal alike.

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的面积，以平方米计

– Field doesn't know

↳ 最大的单体宗教纪念物、建筑的高度，以米计

– Field doesn't know

↳ 一般纪念物、建筑的尺寸，平方米

– Field doesn't know

↳ 一般纪念建筑、纪念物的高度，米

– Field doesn't know

↳ 在最大的定居地，所有宗教纪念物、纪念建筑总体面积所占区域百分比是多少？

– Percentage of area: 0

有不同种类的宗教纪念性建筑物吗？

– No

Notes: In addition to cathedrals, colonial-era Christian cemeteries are common in the Himalayas.

是否存在表征标志

– Yes

↳ 表征在哪里显示【多选】

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Notes: For some Hindu tribals, the lack of certain Hindu body markers (dupatta and tikka, for example) are themselves indicative of Christian conversion -- a kind of iconography through absence. Typically Christian iconography take the form of poster art and statues and associated symbols (crosses, for example) in homes, cars, public buses, churches and so on.

↳ 宗教团体的表征标志有明显特色吗

– No

Notes: Himalayan tribals do not have distinct aspects of Christian iconography when compared to the larger South Asian context. Their poster art, paintings, statues, crosses and so on are not distinctly Himalayan. I am unaware of iconographic syncretism between tribal religious forms and Christianity. At the level of theology, however, syncretism is to be expected.

是否有专门的地点用于神圣行活动或者被认为是神圣的：

– Yes

↳ 神圣场地是否适应环境特点：

“环境特点”指的是风景、山水、罗盘方位等等的特征。

– No

Notes: Churches and cathedrals, often of colonial construction. Among some tribal groups, miraculous faith healing has created sacred sites in unlikely places (such as village mud huts).

有朝圣活动吗：

– No

信仰

埋葬和来世

是否存在精神-肉体的区分

只有当人格（或意识）随肉体死亡而消亡时回答“否”。回答是并不一定意味着存在笛卡尔精神/肉体二元论，而只意味着人格（或意识）的一些要素在肉体死后尚存。

– Yes

↳ 精神 – 心灵被认为具有异乎其它身体部位的能力或特质

– Yes

Notes: Spirit transcends death; the body is temporal and rots.

对来世的信仰：

– Yes

↳ 该宗教团体对来世的空间位置有具体描述吗

– Yes

↳ 来世在这个世界之外的特定领域空间：

– Yes

Notes: Heaven is understood to be a realm existing outside this world (based on various biblical references, such as (John 14:1-3 -- Jesus is actively preparing a place for believers in Heaven; preparing a place for us to live; and Isaiah 65:21 -- believers will plant vineyards and eat eat of the produce).

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“上面”的空间：

– Yes

Notes: Although the Bible goes to some length to describe the placeness of Heaven, most tribal Christians in the Himalayas describe eternal life in Heaven in material and spiritual terms and less in spatial qualities.

↳ 来世被模糊定义为“下面”的空间：

– Yes

Notes: Hell is variously described in the Bible as a below space of eternal damnation -- as a burning sulfuric lake (Revelations 21:8) and as a downwards realm of the dead (Psalms 9:17).

↳ 来世被模糊定义为某个平行空间：

– No

↳ 来世在“其他”空间：

– Yes [specify]: Catholics believe in Purgatory as an intermediate space of purification.

在这个世界上的转世

– No

Notes: However, for many Christian tribals in the Himalayas their Buddhist/Hindu backgrounds continue to shape their innermost conceptions of karma/rebirth and oftentimes put believers in a social bind when it comes time to perform death rituals of kin.

对信众的遗体有特别处置吗：

– No

埋葬过程中或者墓穴中是否存在一起殉葬现象

– No

是否存在陪葬品：

– No

有正式的葬礼吗：

– Yes

↳ 树立纪念碑：

– No

↳ 葬于公墓：

– Yes

Notes: However, Christian tribals in the Himalayas sometimes immolate corpses because of community pressure. This leads to theological concern about the state of the soul.

↳ 葬于家庭墓地或教堂地下室

– No

↳ 在家里（埋在房屋地下或者在有正常家庭活动的地方）

– No

↳ 其他正式的葬礼形式：

– No

超自然存在

有超自然存在吗：

– Yes

↳ 有一个至上之神存在

– Yes

↳ 至上之神是人形：

– Yes

Notes: According to standard Trinitarian beliefs, the supreme high god is one but in

three forms including the incarnate human-divine form of Jesus Christ.

↳ 至上之神是天神

– Yes

↳ 至上之神是地府的神灵（地底世界的）：

– No

Notes: Although God in a sense authorizes the underworld and is described as having traveled there to retrieve the Keys of Life and Death (Hebrews 2:14, among others).

↳ 至上之神与君主不分（王=至高的神）

– No

↳ 君主被视作至上之神的表现和化身：

– No

↳ 至上之神和精英阶层有亲属关系

– No

Notes: Although some tribal Christians have fascinating exegetical moves and hermenutic strategies to link up their lifeways and ancestry with Christ. For example, Gaddi Dalits in Himachal Pradesh describe how Jesus was revealed to shepherds and has special blessings and relationship to shepherds like themselves.

↳ 至上之神和精英有其它类型的效忠关系

– No

↳ 至高之神是不可质疑的善

– Yes

↳ 至上之神的其他特征：

– Yes [specify]: The hermenutic twist of tribal Christians in the Himalayas is how God is localized and harmonized with existing tribal culture, lifeways and beliefs.

↳ 至上之神具有关于这个世界的知识：

– Yes

↳ 至上之神只对特定的领域的人类事务有所认知：

– No

- ↳ 至上之神的知识限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：
 - No
- ↳ 至上之神的知识在采样地区没有限制：
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神的知识对采样地区以外没有限制：
 - Yes
- ↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，至上之神都可以看到你
 - Yes
- ↳ 不论你身处何处，至上之神都可以看到你（即便在黑暗中、在家里）：
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神可以看穿你的心/脑（隐秘的动机）：
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神知道你将来的人生际遇/你将来会做什么（预测的能力）：
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神关于这个世界有其他知识：
 - Yes [specify]: Omniscient and yet this doesn't imede free will.
- ↳ 至上之神对这个世界能够有意施发因果效力：
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神能奖赏
 - Yes
- ↳ 至上之神能惩罚：
 - Yes

↳ 至上之神对这个世界上可以施发间接的因果效力：
– Yes

↳ 至上之神展现其积极的情感：
– Yes

↳ 至上之神展现其负面的情感：
– Yes

↳ 至上之神有饥饿感：
– No

↳ 除了至高之神以外，允许崇拜其他超自然存在吗：
– No
Notes: Not permissible, although common.

↳ 至上之神具备/展现出其他一些特征：
– Field doesn't know

↳ 至上之神和生灵有沟通：
– Yes

↳ 在清醒状态下的日常生活中：
– Yes

↳ 在睡梦中：
– Yes

↳ 在被附体催眠状态中：
– Yes

↳ 通过占卜行为：
– Yes

↳ 只通过宗教专业人员：
– No

↳ 只通过君主：

– No

↳ 其他与生灵的交流方式：

– Yes [specify]: Intercession, possession, tongues.

↳ 过去人的灵魂是存在的：

– No

↳ 有非人类的超自然存在：

– Yes

↳ 这些超自然存在可以被看到：

– Yes

Notes: Among Catholics, supernatural beings can be benevolent patron saints; among Evangelicals and Protestants, supernatural beings are more often demonic forces that can take specific forms. For example, Hali Gaddis (in Himachal Pradesh) believe that evil spirits associated with the devil in Christianity either inhabit Hindu deities or manifest as Hindu deities.

↳ 这些超自然存在可以用身体感触到：

– Yes

Notes: Oftentimes maliciously.

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有认知：

– Yes

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于特定的领域人类事务：

– Yes

↳ 非人类的超自然存在的所知限于采样地区的（一个或多个）特定区域：

– No

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区内无所不知：

– Yes

Notes: Angels and heavenly beings can intercede in believers' lives multifarious ways; demonic spirits can exert malign influence in similar ways.

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对采样地区以外无所不知：

— Yes

↳ 不论你（在公共场所）置身何处，非人类的超自然存都可以看到你：

— Yes

↳ 不论你置身何处非人类的超自然存在都可以看到你（比如在黑暗中和家里）：

— Yes

Notes: Psalms 139:7-11 Where can I go from Your Spirit? Or where can I flee from Your presence? If I ascend to heaven, You are there; If I make my bed in Sheol, behold, You are there. If I take the wings of the dawn, If I dwell in the remotest part of the sea, even there Your hand will lead me, and Your right hand will lay hold of me.

↳ 非人类的超自然存在可以看穿你的心/脑中（隐秘的动机）：

— Yes

Notes: Proverbs 15:3 The eyes of the LORD are in every place, Watching the evil and the good.

↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你的基本特征个性（个人本质）：

— Yes

↳ 非人类的超自然存在知道你将来的人生际遇／你将会做什么（预测未来的能力）：

— Yes

Notes: Ephesians 1:11 In him we were also chosen, having been predestined according to the plan of him who works out everything in conformity with the purpose of his will...

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界有其他的认知：

— Yes [specify]: Depending on personal beliefs and interpretations of the Bible, supernatural beings (of good and evil design) have more or less jurisdiction over people's lives and futures.

↳ 非人类的超自然存在对这个世界可以有意施发因果效应：

— Yes

↳ 这些超自然存在可以奖赏：

— Yes

Notes: Revelations 22:12 Behold, I am coming quickly, and My reward is with Me,

to render to every man according to what he has done...

↳ 这些超自然存在可以惩罚：

— Yes

Notes: Proverbs 3:11-12 My son, do not reject the discipline of the Lord or loathe His reproof, For whom the Lord loves He reproofs, even as a father corrects the son in whom he delights...

↳ 这些超自然存在对这个世界有间接的因果效应：

— Yes

Notes: As commonly practiced, Christianity among Himalayan tribals is associated with indirect causal efficacy in diverse arenas of personal welfare, harvest size, livestock productivity and so on.

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出积极的情感：

— Yes

Notes: When heavenly.

↳ 这些超自然存在展现出负面的情感：

— Yes

Notes: When evil.

↳ 这些超自然存在有饥饿感：

— No

Notes: Not in the Hindu/Buddhist sense. However, in 1 Peter 5:8 Satan is described as possessing a kind of symbolic hunger. "Be sober-minded; be watchful. Your adversary the devil prowls around like a roaring lion, seeking someone to devour."

↳ 这些超自然存在有/展现出一些其他特征：

— Yes [specify]: Evil spirits have various theological characteristics as outlined in Christian demonology.

Notes: According to Revelations 12:7-9, demons are evil angels and have similar features of their heavenly counterparts. Demons are not omniscient but may have specific knowledge within a certain domain. They are not omnipotent but constrained to the power that God allows them to possess.

↳ 有半人半神的存在：

— No

Notes: This depends on terminology and the ways in which one considers Christ as human, divine or "mixed".

↳ 宗教团体具有多种超自然存在：

– Yes

↳ 以基于家庭模式的亲属关系编排：

– No

↳ 按照高下阶层编排：

– Yes

Notes: Demonic spirits within Christian cosmology are often overlaid onto tribal Hindu/Buddhist nature spirits/pantheonic deities. These deities are ranked by their potency and ability to harm.

↳ 各自的权力是限于所属领域的：

– Yes

Notes: As demonic spirits within Christianity are often overlapping with local tribal/animist/Hindu/Buddhist spirits, such spirits are often localized in places.

↳ 万神庙的其他组织方式：

– No

超自然监督

是否存在超自然的监视：

“超自然监视”是指超自然存在监视人类的行为以及或者思想，特别是涉及到社会准则或潜在性违规的情况。

– Yes

↳ 有针对遵守亲社会规范的超自然监视：

亲社会规范是指增加族群中成员协作的规范，包括明显的“道德”或“伦理”规范，也延伸至关于履行合约与誓言，提供热情款待，在紧急情况下互相帮助等等。

– Yes

Notes: As practiced elsewhere, tribal Christianity in the Himalayas is concerned with ethical norms as outlined in the Bible and enforced by God.

↳ 超自然存在在意禁忌：

– Yes

↳ 食物：

– Yes

Notes: The Christian God is generally opposed to animal sacrifice. In John 1:29, Jesus is described as the "Lamb of God who takes away the sin of the world." Among Himalayan tribal Christians, they must often negotiate social expectations to participate and even host goat/sheep sacrifices as prosocial feast rituals and Christian beliefs banning such behavior as taboo.

↳ 神圣空间 :

– Yes

Notes: Not to desecrate churches, for example.

↳ 神圣物品

– Yes

Notes: Not to desecrate sacred objects. However, such prohibitions are considerably less in Christianity than "typical" expressions of tribal religion.

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事项 :

– Yes [specify]: They care about the interior spaces of belief.

↳ 超自然存在关切教友之间的杀害 :

– Yes

Notes: Jesus warned that those who take the sword perish by the sword. Murder is prohibited. However, in 1 John 3:15 Jesus states that "Everyone who hates his brother is a murderer, and you know that no murderer has eternal life abiding in him."

↳ 超自然存在关切其他宗教的信徒的谋杀 :

– Yes

↳ 超自然存在关切其它政权成员的谋杀 :

– Yes

↳ 超自然存在关注性行为 :

– Yes

↳ 通奸 :

– Yes

Notes: Hebrews 13:4 Let marriage be held in honor among all, and let the marriage bed be undefiled, for God will judge the sexually immoral and adulterous.

↳ 乱伦 :

– Yes

Notes: Leviticus 18:10 The nakedness of your son's daughter or your daughter's daughter, their nakedness you shall not uncover; for their nakedness is yours.

↳ 其他性行为：

– Yes [specify]: All manner of "sexual perversions" as scattered throughout the Bible.

↳ 超自然存在在意撒谎行为：

– Yes

Notes: Proverbs 12:22 Lying lips are an abomination to the Lord, but those who deal faithfully are His delight.

↳ 超自然存在在意誓言的执行：

– Yes

Notes: Leviticus 5:4 Or if a person swears thoughtlessly with his lips to do evil or to do good, in whatever matter a man may speak thoughtlessly with an oath, and it is hidden from him, and then he comes to know it, he will be guilty in one of these.

↳ 超自然存在在意懒惰：

– Yes

Notes: Proverbs 10:26 Like vinegar to the teeth and smoke to the eyes, so is the lazy one to those who send him.

↳ 超自然存在在意巫术：

– Yes

Notes: Deuteronomy 18:10 There shall not be found among you anyone who makes his son or his daughter pass through the fire, one who uses divination, one who practices witchcraft, or one who interprets omens, or a sorcerer... However, it is notable that tribal Christians often understand the vicissitudes of life as sorcery done against them (jadu tona in India) and sometimes employ the services of witchdoctors (mantra-tantra, celas) to combat sorcery with sorcery -- despite Christian prohibitions.

↳ 超自然存在在意非致命的打斗：

– Yes

↳ 超自然存在在意规避风险：

– No

↳ 超自然存在在意对长者的不敬：

– No

Notes: Respect for elders (although laid down in biblical verses) is not central to Christian practice as it is among Hindu/Buddhist practice. This often leads to the overthrow of traditional authority that causes social rupture among tribal groups divided by Christian conversion.

↳ 超自然存在在乎说长道短的行为：

– Yes

↳ 超自然存在在意财产犯罪：

– Yes

↳ 超自然存在在乎对仪礼的正确奉守：

– Yes

Notes: However, Christian practice is notably less focused on correctness of ritual observance than tribal religion and Hinduism/Buddhism.

↳ 超自然存在在乎仪式的演绎：

– Yes

Notes: Less than tribal religious traditions, however.

↳ 超自然存在在意度化无宗教信仰者：

– Yes

Notes: Mark 16:15 He said to them, "Go into all the world and preach the gospel to all creation."

↳ 超自然存在在意经济上的公平：

– Yes

Notes: Although the radical economic egalitarianism of Jesus's teachings (aligned with Zealotry) is not often prioritized among tribal Christians in the Himalayas (or really anywhere else for that matter).

↳ 超自然存在在意个人卫生：

– Yes

Notes: 1 Corinthians 6:20 For you were bought with a price. So glorify God in your body. However, Christian expressions in the Himalayas are markedly less focused on personal and symbolic hygiene. For example, Hali Christians (part of the Gaddi tribal community in Himachal Pradesh) drink from the same cup during Communion (Prabhu Bhoj) in an act of group solidarity that violates "normal" Hindu hygiene about the sharing of utensils between members of different castes.

↳ 超自然存在在意其他事物：

– Field doesn't know

超自然存在施加惩罚吗：

– Yes

↳ 超自然惩罚的来源或是动因是已知的吗：

– Yes

↳ 只由至上之神完成

– Yes

Notes: God allows the punishment of sin.

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

– No

↳ 由客观的因果定律来完成：

– No

Notes: Punishment for sin is not causal in a karmic sense since Jesus's death allows for unrequited forgiveness.

↳ 由其他实体或其他方式完成【请注明】：

– Field doesn't know

↳ 超自然惩罚的存在原因是已知的吗：

– Yes

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

– Yes

↳ 为了强制实施团体准则：

– Yes

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

– Yes

↳ 随机：

– No

↳ 其它【请注明】

– Field doesn't know

↳ 超自然惩罚在来世施行：

– Yes

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然惩罚：

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the tribal Christian community in question, eternal damnation can be highly emphasized.

↳ 来世的惩罚包括轻微的感觉不悦：

– No

↳ 来世的惩罚包括极度的感觉的不悦：

– Yes

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世成为低等生命形式：

– No

Notes: Although tribal Christians often retain certain karmic attitudes about reincarnation despite Christian opposition to it.

↳ 来世的惩罚包括转世到低级领域：

– No

Notes: The soul moves from this world into hell. Not a reincarnation.

↳ 其它【请注明】

– No

↳ 超自然惩罚在今世施行：

– Yes

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然惩罚：

– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括噩运：

– No

Notes: Not in the sense often stressed in tribal religion.

↳ 今世的惩罚包括政治上的失败：

– No

↳ 今世的惩罚包括在战斗中失败：

– No

↳ 今世的惩罚包括农作物欠收或恶劣天气：

– Yes

Notes: Tribal Christians are divided about the effects of sin in this life. Certainly eternal damnation in the next life is guaranteed without proper forgiveness. In this life, believers are divided about the impact of sin on everyday domains of crop failure, weather, defeat, misfortune and so on. The so-called Prosperity Gospel so popular in the USA has vague resonance in the Himalayas depending on the sectarian emphasis and the imagination of the believer.

↳ 今世的惩罚包括出游上灾祸：

– No

↳ 今世的惩罚包括轻微的感官的不悦：

– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括强烈的感官的不悦：

– Yes

Notes: Depends on individual belief.

↳ 今世的惩罚包括疾病：

– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括生育上出问题：

– Yes

↳ 今世的惩罚包括后代承受噩运：

– Yes

Notes: The inter-generational curses outlined in the Bible resonate with tribal religious beliefs.

↳ 其它【请注明】

– No

– Field doesn't know

超自然存在赐予奖赏吗：

– Yes

↳ 超自然奖赏的来源/目的是已知的吗：

– Yes

↳ 只由至高的神完成：

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 6:19-21 Do not lay up for yourselves treasures on earth, where moth and rust destroy and where thieves break in and steal, but lay up for yourselves treasures in heaven, where neither moth nor rust destroys and where thieves do not break in and steal. For where your treasure is, there your heart will be also.

↳ 由许多超自然存在完成：

– No

↳ 由客观的因果定律完成：

– No

↳ 为了实现宗教的仪式-崇拜的信奉：

– Yes

Notes: Storing up treasure in heaven is based on devotion and giving glory to God in this world.

↳ 为了推行团体规范：

– No

Notes: Although this is a consequence of such beliefs, it is not its point of origination.

↳ 为了阻止自私自利：

– No

↳ 随机：

– No

↳ 在来世赐予超自然奖赏：

– Yes

↳ 宗教团体非常强调来世的超自然奖赏：

— Yes

Notes: Among Hali Protestant converts in Kangra, for example, weekly services in local house churches emphasized the supernatural rewards of the afterlife as compensation of sorts of this-worldly injustices.

↳ 来世的奖赏包括轻微的感官愉悦：

— Yes

Notes: John 14:2 In my Father's house are many rooms. If it were not so, would I have told you that I go to prepare a place for you?

↳ 来世的奖赏包括极度的感官愉悦：

— Yes

Notes: 1 Corinthians 2:9 But, as it is written, "What no eye has seen, nor ear heard, nor the heart of man imagined, what God has prepared for those who love him."

↳ 来世的奖赏包括永恒的幸福：

— Yes

Notes: John 3:16 For God so loved the world, that he gave his only Son, that whoever believes in him should not perish but have eternal life.

↳ 来世的奖赏包括转世为更高级生命形式：

— No

↳ 来世的奖赏包括投生到更高级的领域中：

— No

↳ 其它【请注明】

— No

↳ 在今世赐予超自然奖赏：

— Yes

↳ 宗教团体非常强调今世的超自然奖赏：

— Yes

Notes: This depends on the sect and the emphasis of individual teachers and believers. Among Hali converts in Hali, for example, this-world rewards were praised weekly during a time to give testimonials about the supernatural blessings given to individual church members. Pastor Vinay gave this speech one Sunday, by way of example: There is so much suffering in the world. And we thank you God for keeping us safe, for

maintaining our life (jīvit rakhnā); there are many people who have not made it to see today, died from diseases and accidents, from so many factors outside human control they have left this world. We thank you God (śukraguzār karnā) for taking care of us in every moment, in every situation. Hallelujah? Hallelujah! I often hear the testimonies from believers, how we are saved by the hand of God from daily accidents, like falling on the road at night, getting a wound and needing to go the hospital. These things happen all the time, but we live in the grace of God and are saved. He doesn't permit these things.

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好运：

– No

↳ 今世的奖赏包括政治上的成功或权力：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括在战斗的胜利：

– No

↳ 今世的奖赏包括和平或社会稳定：

– Yes

Notes: Especially with regard to discrimination and social/caste exclusion and the lack of state support that falls to the weakest and often marginalized groups within tribes.

↳ 今世的奖赏包括好的收成或风调雨顺：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括出行上一路顺风：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括轻微的感觉愉悦：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括极度的感觉愉悦：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括更好的健康：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括多子多孙：

– Yes

↳ 今世的奖赏包括子孙多福

– Yes

↳ 其它【请注明】

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural rewards are described as testimonials in house services among many tribal Christians. Below are categories of supernatural blessings recorded among Hali tribal aspirants in Kangra. In-church testimonials can be roughly categorized as pertaining to: a) safety (“I went to Ludhiana for the first time, and there was no problem while traveling and God helped me to get there safely.”); b) avoidance of disaster (“A few days ago I got distracted, and thank God that his concentration always falls on us because my daughter went on the roof and was horsing around, and thank God my landlord heard her and went and grabbed her and brought her inside, and there was no accident and she didn’t fall.”); c) procurement of work (“I was sitting around not getting any work, and I prayed to God, give me anything! I gave God all my anxieties – there should be work! Finally, the phone call came and I got work, and I was so happy that I didn’t even properly hear the name of where I was supposed to go.”); d) family discord (“My family members are always fighting but thanks to Yeśu Masīh I was able to pray and not get drawn into it.”); e) spiritual torment (“I went to Bharmaur for work and fell into a depression. I couldn’t eat a thing. I was vomiting. I felt like no one could take me out of my sadness. I went to the hospital, but the doctor did nothing. I was feeling so small. I prayed to the Lord (Prabhu), and he touched my body with his Holy Spirit (pavitra ātmā) and removed the evil spirt.”); and f) negotiation of Gaddi identity (“I returned to Bharmaur, and my relatives were bothering me about how I left our Gaddi family deities. They told me about all the things their deities did for them. I told them, ‘It’s okay, keep your deities, they are not for me. My God created the heavens and the earth and sustains me in health. Before I was sick; now I am healed.’”).

救世主/末世论

是否存在救世主信仰：

– Yes

↳ 是否存在救世主的下落或者得知的时间？

– No

Notes: Matthew 24:36 But about that day or hour no one knows, not even the angels in heaven, nor the Son, but only the Father.

↳ 救世主的目的是已知的吗：

– Yes

↳ 救世主是匡复政治统治的政治人物：

– No

↳ 救世主是匡复宗教团体的神职人员：

– No

↳ 其它目的：

– Yes [specify]: The Second Coming of Christ has various interpretations (Preterism, LDS, Evangelical and so on).

规范与道德现实

该宗教团体规定总体性的社会准则了吗：

– Yes

该宗教团体存在传统和道德范畴的区分吗：

– Yes

↳ 这种区别的性质是什么：

– Present and clear

↳ 宗教团体对道德规范有专门规定吗：

– Yes

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的观念模糊有不明显的联系：

– Yes

Notes: As many tribals are non-literate, explicit biblical exegesis is not the norm.

↳ 专门的道德规范和模糊的形而上学的实体有明显的联系：

– Yes

↳ 专门的道德规范和客观的宇宙秩序的有联系（比如业力）：

– Yes

↳ 专门的道德规范以某种方式和人形的存在相联系：

– Yes

Notes: Anthropomorphic in the sense of Jesus as incarnate God in human flesh.

↳ 专门的道德规范和人形化的存在的命令有明显的联系：

– Yes

↳ 专门的道德规范和形而上的没有特别联系：

– No

↳ 道德规范适用于：

– All individuals within society

Notes: The egalitarianism and lack of social exception based on caste and class is a major attraction for low-status converts within tribes. This speaks to a larger issue about the inegalitarianism of tribes and the appeal for Christianity among those commonly discriminated against in tribal social formations.

该宗教团体是否有提倡的核心重要美德：

– No

Notes: However, particular tribal converts may emphasize different virtues (such as social equality) based on their own subject positionality within the larger community. Emphasizing such virtues of equality may restructure social behavior.

常规

会员费用和惯例

该宗教团体要求成员禁欲(完全禁绝性生活)吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员节制性行为(部分禁止性生活)吗：

– Yes

↳ 一夫一妻制 (男性)：

– Yes

↳ 一夫一妻制 (女性)：

– Yes

↳ 其他性行为的限制 (男性)：

– Yes

Notes: Among some tribal groups, forms of marriage exchange (like batta satta among Gaddis wherein the bride's brother would marry the groom's sister or vice versa) and polygamy have

fallen away, although sexual laws are still comparatively lax in an Indian context. Christian converts are further instructed in biblical teachings about chastity and sexual purity.

↳ 其他性行为的限制（女性）：

– Yes

Notes: The wearing of the ghunghat (dupatta headdress) is sometimes practices to encourage sexual modesty.

该宗教团体要求成员阉割吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员斋戒吗：

– No

Notes: Not required, but some Christians draw from passages in the Bible and practice fasting.

该宗教团体要求成员断除某些食物（对想吃的食物的禁忌）吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员在身体上留下永久性疤痕或作疼痛的修整吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员忍受疼痛的身体姿势或暂时性的伤口吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成年成员的牺牲生命吗

“成年”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义中的超过18周岁的并且为他/她的行为负法律责任的人类，那么请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

– No

该宗教团体要求儿童成员的牺牲吗

“儿童”在此指该文化中主位或本土的类别；如果此类别不同于主流西方定义，请在评论/来源中注明：以下文本框。

– No

该宗教团体要求成员自我牺牲（自杀）吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员贡献出财产／昂贵的物品吗：

– No

该宗教团体要求成员奉献出自己的时间吗（例如参加会议或仪式，常规祷告等）：

– Yes

Notes: Adherents are instructed to attend church regularly (usually in the form of house church attendance).

该宗教团体要求成员承受身体上的风险吗：

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, physical violence is threatened against Christian tribals (see the video about the Ladakhi Christian in "sources". In the case I am most familiar with, Hali Christians in Kangra were visited by Hindu fundamentalists who physically threatened them for worshipping on Sundays.

该宗教团体要求成员接受道德戒律吗：

– Yes

Notes: Interestingly, when tribals become Christian they often adopt ethical norms that are viewed as distinctly untribal by the majority community.

成为该宗教团体的成员会被组外成员边缘化吗：

– Yes

Notes: Like the above answer, when tribals convert to Christianity they are often put in the dilemma of rejecting "tribal" practices like animal sacrifice and the taking of intoxicants.

该宗教团体要求成员参与小规模宗教仪式（私人的，家庭的）吗：

– Yes

Notes: Weekly communion and, in extraordinary situations (that nevertheless happen with some frequency) for prayer intercession to cast out demons and evil spirits -- a practice that parallels witchcraft practices in many tribal communities.

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：
这里表演指小型仪式。

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Among the Halis in Kangra, for example, house churches would meet at regular intervals (normally Sunday mornings) and for special intercession prayer periods -- about once a week.

该宗教团体要求成员参与大规模的宗教仪式吗：

比如，涉及两个或以上的家庭；包括有大规模的“典礼”和“节庆”。

– Yes

↳ 平均来说，大规模的宗教仪式有多少参与者聚集在一个地点：

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Large-scale rituals include yearly Christmas and Easter celebrations. Some tribals are members of house churches that set up tents and small-scale celebratory rituals; other tribals are part of larger institutional churches with massive membership (such as Northeast India) where celebrations happen in the thousands.

↳ 表演间的平均时间间隔是多少（以小时计）：

这里表演指小型仪式。

– Field doesn't know

↳ 是否存在正统性审查：

正统性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细适当阐释的文本等等。

– Yes

Notes: Priesthood or qualified religious leaders (padres, pastors and so on).

↳ 是否存在对仪轨规范性审查：

仪轨规范性审查是用于保证用常规方式阐释仪式的机制。比如，通过专业祭司或者其他系统的管理的显赫监督，诉诸于详细记载适当程序的文本等等。

– No

Notes: Not like Brahmanical checks.

↳ 参与包括完全同步的修行吗：

– No

Notes: Not as a rule, although "tribal practices" do seep into Christian forms of worship and ritual.

↳ 使用酒精饮料吗：

– No

Notes: Tribal Christianity is generally opposed to intoxicants and generally describes drugs and alcohol as not only "tribal backwards" but also anathema to Christian virtue. They draw from a range of biblical sources to make this claim.

除了仪式之外还有群内的的标示性符号吗：

比如，关于外表的特别改变，比如割礼、纹身、牺牲等等。

– Yes

↳ 纹身/身体上疤痕等：

– No

↳ 割礼：

– No

↳ 饮食禁忌：

– Yes

Notes: The banning of prasad (sanctified food) in Hindu/Buddhist traditions. This creates sociality problems as the rejection of food from neighbors and affines is tied into a history of status jockeying and the rejection of the cooker or food presenter (since food is often felt to be a biomorphic substance imbued with the essence of the giver).

↳ 头发：

– No

↳ 装束：

– No

Notes: Although some Christian tribal groups discourage the wearing of traditional tribal costumes -- creating social breaches.

↳ 装饰物

– No

↳ 古老的用于仪式的语言：

– No

↳ 其它：

– Yes [specify]: Markers of Christian identification among tribals are usually noticeable for their absence -- the absence of tikka and maang and dora and choti and other physical body markers associated with some tribal traditions.

团体使用虚拟的亲族称谓吗：

– Yes

↳ 虚拟的亲族称谓是普遍的：

– No

↳ 虚拟的亲族称谓是广泛的：

– Yes

Notes: Adherents become brothers and sisters in Christ, of one body.

使用虚拟的亲族称谓，但不常见：

– No

社会与机构

社会复杂程度

对宗教团体所属社会最恰当的描述为（请选其一）：

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Christian conversion among tribal segments is not often individual but group oriented. Sub-groups and clans/castes with tribal communities may convert not en masse but one after the other. So the "society" of tribal Christians is often a low-status segment. Between tribes, however, there is no widely-recognized Christian society as such.

福利

该宗教团体提供制度化的救助饥荒的服务吗：

– Yes

Notes: From larger denominational churches to small house churches, there are forms of socioeconomic support. When someone is ill or when crops fail, collections/tithes may be taken for that individual family in question.

饥荒救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Yes

Notes: IRDB and poverty assistance in India and elsewhere in the Himalayas.

该宗教团体提供制度化的的贫困救济吗：

– Yes

贫困救济是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Yes

该宗教团体对年老体弱者有制度化的关怀吗：

– No

Notes: Family units and extended relatives are normally responsible for the care of the elderly.

对年老体弱者制度化的关怀是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– No

教育

该宗教团体为信众提供正规教育吗：

– Yes

↳ 正规教育仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

– No

Notes: Many primary and secondary Christian schools are in Nepal and Northeast India. On the other hand, there are many seminaries in the Himalayas that cater to tribal populations and are designed for aspiring religious leaders. For example, the Council of Baptist Churches in Northeast India (with more than 1,000,000 members) in Northeast India has the Eastern Theological College which has minted more than 2500 graduates and 800 pastors.

↳ 男性和女性都能得到这种教育吗：

– Yes

正规教育是通过宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

– Yes

Notes: For example, Agape Christian Missions (<http://acm-india.org/>) is a South Indian group focused on tribes outside of the Indian Himalayas; however, they fund theological training and the dissemination of audio recordings of the bible in local dialects to tribal groups in Himachal Pradesh.

↳ 男性和女性都能得到宗教团体以外的教育吗：

– Yes

官僚机构

团体的信徒与团体内的官方机构有互动吗？

– Yes

Notes: Just in Northeast India, for example, tribal Christians are often affiliated with sectarian churches operated on formal bureaucracies. See, for example, "Church-Mission Dynamics in Northeast India" by Lalsangkima Pachuau (International Bulletin of Missionary Research 27:4).

宗教信众与其他官僚机构有互动吗：

– No

公共工程

该宗教团体储备公共食品吗：

– No

公共食品储备是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– No

该宗教团体提供水资源管理（灌溉、防洪）吗：

– No

水资源管理是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给该团体信众的吗：

– Yes

Notes: State governments and IRDB poverty quotas.

该宗教团体提供基础交通设施吗：

– No

基础交通设施是通过该宗教团体以外的机构提供给团体信众的吗：

– Yes

Notes: State governments. In all the questions relating to public works, the answers are highly variable. It is uncommon for churches in the Himalayas with tribal congregants to provide storage of public food, for example. But the larger institutional churches in the Indian Northeast and Nepal, along with various NGOs and missions groups do offer significant forms of social support and emergency funds for situated problems. And small-scale house churches often collect tithes for redistribution to members suffering from various misfortunes.

纳税

该宗教团体课取税款或什一税吗：

– Yes

Notes: Based on church tradition, congregants are encouraged to give what they can (typically 10% of earned income). This is based on Deuteronomy 14:22 (Make an offering of ten percent, a tithe, of all the produce which grows in your fields year after year).

团体信众的税是由该宗教团体以外的机构来征收吗：

– Yes

Notes: Various state and local taxes.

强制

该宗教团体设有体制化的警务部门吗：

– No

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的警务部门有互动吗：

– Yes

Notes: Many tribal Christians interact with heightened security forces, especially in sensitive border and disputed areas.

该宗教团体设置体制化的法官吗：

– No

宗教团体的信众与外部体制下的司法系统有互动吗：

– Yes

Notes: Legal systems particular to each state/country. Also tribal Christians are often under local judicial systems (panchayat).

该宗教团体施加制度化的处罚吗：

– No

宗教团体的信众承受宗教团体以外的体制下的处罚吗：

– Yes

↳ 制度化的处罚包括死刑吗：

– No

↳ 制度化的处罚包括流放吗：

– No

↳ 制度化的处罚包括体罚吗：

– No

↳ 制度化的处罚包括排挤孤立吗：

– No

↳ 制度化的处罚包括没收财产吗：

– No

该宗教团体有正式的法典吗：

– No

宗教团体的信众受制于外部体制下的法典吗：

– Yes

福利

该宗教团体有体制化的军事力量吗：

– No

宗教团体的信众参加宗教团体以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

– Yes

宗教团体的信众受保护或受治于宗教图案以外机构提供的机制化的军事力量吗：

– Yes

书面语

该宗教团体有自己独特的书面语吗：

– Yes

这种独特的书面语的使用仅限于宗教专职人员吗：

– No

Notes: Although trained pastors and much more likely to be literate than their congregants. For an analysis of the translation of the Bible into tribal dialects in the Himalayas, especially through Summer Language Institute of Linguistics, see Fredrick A. Aldridge Jr's unpublished dissertation on the subject -- available here: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.912.9893&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

团体信众能在宗教团体以外的体制中接触到非宗教专用的书面语吗：

– No

团体信众在宗教团体以外的体制下使用使用非宗教专用的书面语吗：

– No

日历

该宗教团体有正式的历法吗：

– Yes

Notes: Although the Christian calendar is in a sense the standard calendar throughout the Himalayas to mark secular time, the Christian calendar with its distinct religious observances and monthly breakdown differs significantly from how most tribal communities measure time (either using a Hindu calendar (panchang) or animist/Buddhist spiritual time or, as is often the case, using agricultural or pastoral measurements of time).

该宗教团体的信众在宗教团体以外的体制下有正式的历法可用吗：

– No

食物生产

该宗教团体自产食物吗

– No

Notes: Although through redistribution of tithes and international missions works/support church members in distress are often helped -- including food donations.

该宗教团体外的机构向团体信众提供食物吗：

– Yes

请描述食物生产的形式/层级【多选】

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)